

COMMUNICATIVE-PRAGMATIC GROUNDS FOR THE STUDY OF INTRODUCTORY AND INSERTION ELEMENTS.

Djurayeva Shakhlo Gulyamovna

Teacher of SamSIFL

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Abstract: the article deals with the study of introductory and insertion elements, which help communicators during the processes of discourse generation, actualization and perception. The research is based on Communicative-pragmatic aspect .Functional polysemy, a characteristic feature of many discourse marker as English, is realized on two levels – beyond the pragmatic functions of these words and within them.

Key words: discourse markers, polysemy, functional polysemy, Russian language, English language, desemantization.

Communicative-pragmatic studies of introductory and insertion elements represent a linguistic direction within the framework of a system-structural approach to language cognition, the object of which is a language in human activity, a language in the process of interpersonal interaction. In the 20th century, within the framework of a system-structural approach to language cognition under the influence of theoretical developments of the classics of domestic linguistics (A.A. Potebni, J.I.B. Scherby, A.M. Peshkovsky, E.D. Polivanova, L.P. Yakubinsky, V.A. Zvegintseva), prominent domestic psychologists (J.I.C. Vygotsky, N.I. Zhinkina, A.N. Leontyeva, A.R. Luria, S.L. Rubinstein) and foreign researchers (W. von Humboldt, E. Benvenist, L. Wittgenstein, P. Grice, T. van Dyck, C. Morris, D. Austin, C. Pierce, J. Ser la, etc.) a multi-discipline of the communicative-pragmatic direction was formed in linguistics.

The current state of the problem of metalanguage components as a universal syntactic category requires taking into account the anthropocentric factor in language, the behavior of the human person in the process of communication (communicative attitudes and emotional state of participants in speech communication, ways to influence the recipient of speech, etc.).

Based on the concept of human activity, researchers are increasingly paying attention to the social, psychological, pragmatic aspects of the speech behavior of the person. This trend is primarily associated with the problem of learning "language in action," within the framework of which modern linguistic research is being conducted.

A person reports facts and events or indicates reactions to them, verbalizes feelings and desires in a certain way in the process of cognitive activity, verbally forms concepts, thoughts and conclusions, enters into communicative contacts, encourages the interlocutor to this or that action. All this variety of speech needs and manifestations in their communicative completeness is realized primarily through syntax, using the syntactic resources of the language. One of these language resources is the system of introductory elements that has developed in the syntax of the Russian language, forming a "communicative-pragmatic category with the general content of the subjective, evaluative attitude of the speaker to the statement" [LecantPA, 1998:3] and insert elements with varying degrees of communicative setting, which can be qualified "as additional to the content of the main sentence" [Gusarenko C.B., 1999:6] and text of a certain compositional type. The interpretation of introductory words, phrases and inserted sentences is one of the unresolved linguistic problems, although it attracted the attention of many researchers. Thus, linguists have repeatedly turned to the study of the history of introductory words in Russian (I.A. Babakova 1955, V.A. Glukhova 1977), to the consideration of the grammatical and semantic properties of introductory words and phrases (A.I. Anikin 1956, A.I. Studnev 1969, P.A. Markaryan 1987, P.A. Lekant 1988, L.I. I. Vasilenko 1990), to the specifics of the connection of introductory elements with the statement (A.M. Peshkovsky 1938, A.A. Shakhmatov 1941, A.I. Anikin 1956, A.G. Rudnev 1968, I.I. Meshchaninov 1976), to consider introductory units as one of the means of expressing the modality of a sentence (V.V. Vinograd 1950, A.A. Kornilov 1973, B.Z. Panfilov 1977, G.P. Nemets 1991), to the analysis of the modal characteristic of the introductory components (A.I. Ostanin 1968, V.V. Vostokov 1976, E.S. Yakovleva 1984, E.I. Belyaeva 1991, T.I. Steksova 1992, I.V. Stolyarova 1992), to their intonation features (R.M. Romanova 1971, Z.M. Bazarbayeva 1991), to the study of the functioning of introductory and insertion components as part of various types of sentences, as part of the text. A.I. Studneva 1969, M.S. Chertkova 1969, V.V. Amosova 1971, J.I.B. Anisimova 1982, G.A. Zolotova 1983, A.M. Baranov, I.M. Kobozeva 1984, C.B. Gusarenko 1999, Yu.G. Polyakova 2001). Special cases of the union function of introductory components in the structure of the sentence (text) were also considered (M.E. Boskova 1959, N.V. Muravyova 1980, T.S. Algazina 1994)

However, despite the fact that a variety of introductory and insertion elements have long been the subject of close attention of linguists, their interpretation and description methods are still different. Moreover, the

researchers use different terminology, diverse descriptions of these speech elements. So in the works of scientists you can find the terms "introductory words and phrases" (A.N. Baranov, M.E. Boskova, V.I. Bukharin, D.I. Ganich, I.M. Kobozeva, V.M. Nikitin, A.I. Ostanin), "introductory-modal words" (J.I.B. Anisimova, G.A. Zolotova), "introductory" or "introductory-allied components" (T.S. Algazina, J.I.K. Dmitrieva, P.A. Lekant, I.V. Stolyarova), and "introductory-modal units" (V.V. Amosova), "introductory constructions" (E.M. Galkina-Fedoruk, P.I. Sedun), "introductory words and revolutions" (E.V. Paducheva), "introductory sentences, insertion elements, inserts, insertion structures" (C.B. Gusarenko, A.I. Studnev), "introductory statements" (E.H. Gorbachev), etc.

In this study, following V.V. Vostokov, A.A. Kornilov, V.Ya. Plotkin, N.V. Rachuk, M.N. Rudkovskaya, Yu.M. Skrebnev, we consider it possible to call the considered speech units "introductory and insertion elements," combining both introductory words and introductory phrases, and introductory sentences and introductory sentences inserted constructs, since they are not all related to the sentence syntactically, "express the speaker's relation to the thought being expressed" (Grammar 1980, E.M. Galkina-Fedoruk 1958, T.G. Venerable 1968, A.N. Gondev 1973, N.S. Valgin 1991), that is, they may contain indications of the degree of reliability of the message, the nature of the action, may express an emotional assessment of the statement, indicate its source, contain comments on the use of words, style and tone of speech, establish a connection between this message and previous or subsequent and have a special intonation (P.M. Romanova 1971, Z.M. Bazarbaeva 1991) At the same time, introductory and insertion elements are one of the means characteristic of the connection between independent sentences in the text. Linguistic studies of the last decade of the 20th century clearly define the contours of new concepts focused on the study of the corpus of introductory and insertion elements of the modern Russian language within the framework of the general scientific problem "man in language," and in particular - a person creating discourse. This is due to the significant interest of linguists aimed at identifying the communicative specifics and pragmatic properties of introductory and insertion elements.

Achieving this goal in this article involves solving the following tasks:

1. Identify the specifics of the communicative-pragmatic content of the introductory and insertion elements and their integral conditioning;
2. Determine the communicative-pragmatic potential of introductory and insertion elements in the text, their role in optimizing speech communication;

3. Classify introductory elements depending on their implementation of communicative and pragmatic attitudes;

4. Classify the inserted elements depending on their implementation of communicative and pragmatic attitudes both in the statement and in the text as a whole.

The implementation of the set tasks is carried out using the following methods and techniques: a) a descriptive method using techniques of observation, interpretation, comparison, generalization and typology; b) methods of contextual and situational-contextual analysis taking into account situational-deterministic connections of speech units, causes and methods of their use; c) communication method.

1. The study of inserted elements leads to the need to analyze this syntactic phenomenon from the point of view of communicative pragmatics. In this chapter, insertiveness is considered as a special speech technique that makes the reader perceive the information received as double text: text itself and metatext. The obvious isolation from the general text drawing allows the inserted elements to solve a number of pragmatic problems: to equalize the background knowledge of the author and the addressee, to convey the polyphony of the artistic text, to express a subjective attitude to certain realities.

2. The need for meta-language commentary arises for the writer when, given the nature of the perception of his statement by a real or hypothetical addressee, he tries to predict possible questions, objections on his part, which is why the author accompanies the main content of the text with various explanations, amendments, translations and interpretations of words, comments of an evaluative nature. At the first approach to this problem, we identify three groups of communicative-pragmatic insertion elements capable of implementing communicative communicant settings: text-propositive, emotive-no-estimated, contaminated insertion elements.

3. Textpropositive insertion elements at the level of utterance are designed to explain, clarify, supplement the propositional content of utterance. The addressee, when including text-propositive insertion elements in the content of the main statement, solves the following pragmatic problems: he clarifies the information of the main content of the statement by designating a possible alternative situation; transmits information as valid or problematic; focuses the interlocutor's attention on the information presented in the content of the main statement; maximally adapts information transmission to the recipient's perception; reduces the categorical nature of the statement; increases the

reliability of the information due to the cited source; represents the course of reasoning of the communicant.

4. Emotive-evaluative insertion elements vividly express the speaker's emotive-evaluative attitude: to the content of the text, to the genre of the text and to the addressee. Woven into the fabric of the main utterance, emotive-evaluative insertion elements from the point of view of their semantic content are able to implement a number of pragmatic attitudes of the speaker, such as: to introduce positive, negative information in relation to the main utterance described in the main utterance; in relation to himself or the design of the speech statement; create an ironic tonality of utterance; to vua-lyse the categorical statement.

5. Contaminated insertion elements combine communicative-pragmatic load of text-propositive and emotive-estimating insertion elements. The study material made it possible to distinguish the following speech settings when the contaminated insertion elements were introduced into the tissue of the main utterance: to report, clarify or clarify the information necessary for an adequate perception of the thought transmitted by the main utterance; increase the impression of the statement by giving a subjective assessment of the reported; comment on the main statement reported in a more concise or, conversely, detailed form.

The communicative-pragmatic study of the introductory and insertion elements of the modern Russian language is a promising direction of linguistic research, which studies the methods of using the syntactic means of the language, in particular, the introductory and insertion elements in the activity of speech communication in the process of interpersonal interaction.

In speech, introductory elements and insertion elements exist and categorically differ. The introductory element is defined from the standpoint of communicative-pragmatic linguistics as a component of utterance, forming a modal plan and implementing certain communicative-pragmatic attitudes of the speaker. Insertion elements are defined as a special syntactic phenomenon that goes beyond a complicated and complex sentence; insert creates a "double-text" with an inclusive sentence and expresses meta-communicative content.

The parameters that determine the system structure of the communicative-pragmatic situation using input and insertion elements include: a talking subject who implements his communicative settings; the destination receiving the information; the general purpose of communicants, which determines the speech mode of communication and the choice of introductory and insertion

elements of the language as an expression of the subjective position of the speaker.

The communicative setting of the talking subject using the introductory and insertion elements in the activity of speech communication is one of the leading factors of communication and represents a predisposition of the activity of speech communication to the transmission of information using the introductory and insertion elements of the language with the expectation of achieving the predicted result of communication. The communicative installation contains a plan of communicative intentions in the aspect of which the speaker seeks to transmit various information to the addressee through input and insertion elements, as well as a plan of pragmatic calculation with the help of which the communicant plans to achieve a certain result in affecting the addressee.

We believe that from the standpoint of communicative pragmatics, the classification of introductory elements can be presented as follows: accent-but-affirmative, accent-probabilistic, emotive-qualifying, targeted-marked, fatal and metatext introductory elements. The addressee, using accent-affirmative introductory elements, focuses the addressee's attention on all the statement or any part of it, purposefully insists on a certain nomination, knowing that the information is reliable. Accent-probabilistic introductory elements, in certain situations of speech activity, implement pragmatic semantics - various shades of probability, possibilities. Introductory elements having an expressive connotation expressing a positive or negative relation to the content of the utterance are called emotive-qualifying. Targeted-marked introductory elements serve to express the attachment of an opinion or assessment to a particular subject sphere, indicate the source of the message.

The fatal introductory elements implement "this contact" in all three phases of speech communication (establishment, maintenance, opening of speech contact). Metatext introductory elements, as shown by the results of our study, on the one hand, connecting parts of the text (individual sentences, paragraphs) are a specific means of interfacial and interabsorbent communication, and on the other hand, they help the speaker (writer) to solve a number of pragmatic problems: focus the interlocutor's attention on a certain nomination in the text; indicate a greater or lesser degree of significance of a feature in the text; log the text, while revealing the course of reasoning of the communicant; mark the trivial state of affairs; submit an author's comment on a particular topic or situation; to mark emotional evaluability.

Communicative-pragmatic studies of introductory elements make it possible to analyze them in the light of the theory of speech acts - depending on the implementation by the talking subject of a set of communicative attitudes or illocutative intentions. Introductory elements participate in such acts of communication as: acts of indignation, indignation; acts of admiration, delight; acts of opinion, hearing, recognition; acts of fright; acts of sworn assurance; acts of edification, reproach; acts of ridicule, contempt; acts of approval, encouragement; acts of despair; acts of warning, warning; acts of irritation, annoyance; acts of determination; acts of consent, confirmation, reconciliation; acts of surprise, amazement, bewilderment; acts of distrust, doubts. The paper describes three groups of communicative-pragmatic insertion elements capable of implementing communicative installations: text-propositive, emotive-evaluative, contaminated insertion elements.

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Thus, the introductory and insertion elements used in the conditions of communicative-pragmatic activity contain subjective information to the realities of the surrounding reality, and this information, from the point of view of the sender of the voice message, is designed to implement a certain set of communicative settings and effectively affect the addressee.

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